

Technological Sovereignty and ICT Standardisation

Authors:

Knut Blind

Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation
Research & Technische Universität Berlin,
Chair of Innovation Economics

Module Objectives

After completing this module, you should be able:

1. to understand the concept of technological sovereignty.
2. to explain the role of ICT standardisation and standards in contributing to achieving and safeguarding technological sovereignty.
3. to apply the role of ICT standardisation and standards for safeguarding technological sovereignty in specific ICT contexts.
4. to analyse the challenges faced by countries in leveraging ICT standardisation for technological sovereignty.

About The Author

Knut Blind

Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research & Technische Universität Berlin, Chair of Innovation Economics

Knut Blind studied economics, political science, and psychology at Freiburg University. During his studies, he spent one year at Brock University (Canada), where he was awarded a BA. Finally, he earned his Diploma in Economics and later his doctoral degree at Freiburg University. Between 1996 and 2010, he joined the Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, Karlsruhe, Germany, as a senior researcher and, at last, as head of the Competence Center “Regulation and Innovation”. In April 2006, Knut Blind was appointed Professor of Innovation Economics at the Faculty of Economics and Management at the Berlin University of Technology. Between 2008 and 2016, he also held the endowed chair of standardisation at the Rotterdam School of Management of Erasmus University. From April 2010 to September 2019, he was linked to the Fraunhofer Institute of Open Communication Systems in Berlin. Since October 2019, he has been head of the business unit “Innovation and Regulation” at the Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research. In 2012, he initiated both the Berlin Innovation Panel and the German Standardisation Panel followed by a pilot of a European Standardisation Panel launched in 2023. Besides numerous articles on patents, he published several contributions on standardisation and further innovation aspects in refereed journals.

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Technological Sovereignty and ICT Standardisation

1. Introduction

The increasing focus on technological sovereignty has emerged from geopolitical uncertainties, particularly trade conflicts between major powers like the U.S. and China, compounded by the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine. These events have highlighted the importance of ensuring that nations can develop and control critical technologies independently. Technological sovereignty extends beyond merely achieving self-sufficiency; it involves a strategic approach to maintain independence in critical technology sectors while fostering collaborative international relationships.

This module explores the concept of technological sovereignty and the role of standardisation, in particular related to information and communication technology (ICT) as a crucial policy instrument in achieving it. Technological sovereignty is understood as the ability of a nation or organisation to independently control its technological infrastructure and capabilities, thus ensuring security, privacy, and economic competitiveness. As technological advancements continue to shape global dynamics, the importance of establishing robust policies to safeguard technological sovereignty has never been more critical.

While standardisation is increasingly recognized as a vital aspect of technology governance, particularly in ICT, its potential as an effective strategy tool to secure technological sovereignty is often overlooked. Based on the literature, mechanisms of standardisation and standards, highlighting how they can serve as protective measures against external dependencies and vulnerabilities. We reveal that through standardisation and standards, countries can enhance their technological capacities, ensuring that they are not solely reliant on foreign technologies.

Then, several propositions are derived related to the effectiveness of standardisation and standards as a safeguard for technological sovereignty. By analysing mobile communication standardisation, we elucidate how various safeguard mechanisms operate within the context of mobile technologies, providing insights into their effectiveness in enhancing national autonomy in technology.

Moreover, recommendations are presented suggesting actionable strategies for stakeholders—governments, industry leaders, and standardisation bodies—to strengthen technological sovereignty. These implications underscore the need for coherent policies that integrate standardisation efforts into broader technological strategies.

Finally, the course addresses the challenges that standardisation and standards face in the pursuit of technological sovereignty, particularly in an evolving geopolitical landscape. As nations navigate complex international relations and competitive technological environments, understanding these challenges will be vital for developing effective policies that secure technological independence and resilience in the future.

2. Definition of Technological Sovereignty and basic understanding

Technological sovereignty includes several dimensions, such as knowledge, research, development, production, operation, usage, and transparency. The alternative concept of open strategic autonomy (Cagnin et al., 2021) advocates for a comprehensive policy approach that spans geopolitics, economics, law, technology, and data governance. The discussion around technological sovereignty emphasizes autonomy rather than autarky, focusing on collaboration while avoiding over-reliance on external sources.

Eventually, we refer to the definition of technological sovereignty by Edler et al. (2023):
 “Ability of a state or a federation of states to develop technologies it deems critical for its welfare, competitiveness, and ability to act or source them from other economic areas without one-sided structural dependency”.

3. Standardisation and standards safeguarding mechanisms for Technological Sovereignty

Standardisation plays a pivotal role in achieving technological sovereignty. It facilitates knowledge transfer, supports innovation, and enhances trade relations. Standards, particularly those set by recognised standard-setting organisations (SSOs), like ISO and IEC, provide frameworks that nations can leverage to secure their technological capabilities.

The European Commission's communication "Shaping Europe's Digital Future" (European Commission, 2020) underscores the importance of European technological sovereignty, highlighting compliance with European standards as essential for accessing the EU single market. The EU aims to set global standards in critical areas such as 5G technology, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity, which are crucial for maintaining technological sovereignty amidst global competition.

Although there is no established conceptual framework, the approach focuses on innovation, trade, and public policies, particularly the regulatory framework, as essential instruments to assure technological sovereignty (e.g., Edler et al., 2020) because they can immediately be supported by standardisation and standards, particularly in ICT. The starting point of the elaboration is standardisation as a knowledge and technology transfer channel (Blind and Gauch, 2009, Blind et al., 2024) and its interlinkages to other channels because it has an essential role for innovation (see a review by Blind 2022). Furthermore, standards influence trade flows (Swann 2010) and therefore eventually technological sovereignty. Finally, standards play in the context of the European Union (EU) an essential role for the specification and eventually the implementation of regulations and other public policies, in particular, to generate an innovation fostering framework (e.g., Blind 2016). According to the recent EU standardisation strategy (European Commission, 2022), standardisation specifying technical regulations will play an even more critical role to secure competitiveness and values of EU.

Table 1: Standardisation and standards as safeguarding mechanisms for technological sovereignty
 (Source: based on Blind, 2025, p.6)

Driver	Description	Safeguarding mechanism related to technological sovereignty
Human Resources	Involvement of researchers and experts in standardisation processes Indirectly, HR are the essential requirement for R&D and innovation activities	to secure TS by integrating own contents, preventing other countries' content and keep technology use open
R&D	Implicit and proprietary R&D results as input in standardisation processes	to secure TS by integrating own contents, preventing other countries' content and keep technology use open
Publications	Publications can be the base for standards	to secure TS by diffusing their contents broadly and in general without limitations
Patents	Patents declared to be standard-essential	to secure TS by being available for all companies world-wide and, therefore, countries interested in implementing the standards
Software	Software, particularly Open Source Software, can be the base for standards	to secure TS by being available according to the applicable Open Source licenses for all companies and countries interested in implementing the standards

Innovation	Involvement in standardisation and the implementation of standards can promote the innovation capabilities of companies and countries	securing TS by generating product innovation expanding the already existing products and set of suppliers
Trade	Involvement in standardisation and the implementation of standards can promote the capabilities of companies and companies to trade goods and services	securing TS by promoting export and import of goods for a larger group of companies and countries
Policy/Regulation	Policy initiatives, like public procurement referring to international standards or referencing standards in regulations	can secure TS by expanding the number of companies being able to deliver products to public tenders and by harmonizing the regulatory frameworks across countries

Based on the drivers for technology sovereignty listed in Table 1 and references to already available empirical evidence, we derive the following propositions related to standardisation's and standards' role as safeguards for technological sovereignty in general and ICT in particular:

- R&D active countries can influence the trajectories in standardisation processes to secure their technological sovereignty (Blind and von Laer, 2022)
- Standards can serve as a backup for technological sovereignty for those countries that do not invest heavily in R&D, similar to their hedging function for companies (Foucart and Li, 2021). However, a minimum level of R&D is necessary to ensure countries' absorptive capacity (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990) to implement them, e.g., in developing countries (Zoo et al., 2017).
- Patent-active countries can influence both the direction of standardisation processes in particular in ICT (Buggenhagen and Blind, 2022) and the implementation especially of ICT standards, e.g., via economically feasible licensing conditions (FRAND) and, therefore, technological sovereignty.
- Standardisation and standards are more critical for assuring technological sovereignty related to hardware in particular in ICT, whereas OSS is more relevant for software and digital sovereignty
- Public procurement can promote the implementation of international standards to increase the diversity in the supply chain, e.g., supporting innovative start-ups and SMEs to secure countries' technological sovereignty.
- International standards are crucial for supporting domestic exporters' competitive advantage and promoting imports (Swann, 2010), which is even more relevant for technological sovereignty.
- In particular, international standards can complement the primarily nationally specified regulations in heavily regulated sectors to secure technological sovereignty by promoting innovation (Blind and Münch, 2024) and a broad portfolio of suppliers.
- If governmental regulations are not necessarily needed, international standards can provide an open, innovation-friendly framework for emerging technologies, securing countries' technological sovereignty.

4. Mobile communication standardisation as an illustration

The development of mobile communication standards, particularly 5G, serves as an illustrative case. 5G technology is critical for national infrastructure and poses unique challenges and opportunities for technological sovereignty. Active participation in 5G standardisation can enhance a nation's technological capabilities and promote economic competitiveness.

Table 2 summarizes the drivers for technological sovereignty and the safeguard mechanism of standardisation and standards related to 5G. Furthermore, there is first empirical evidence about these linkages. However, this evidence does not exist for all of the driving forces and is often not always 5G-specific. Furthermore, the limited evidence represents just a snapshot, i.e., correlations, and does not allow the derivation of causal relationships.

Table 2: ICT standardisation and standards as safeguarding mechanisms for technological sovereignty related to 5G (Sources in brackets) (Source: Blind, 2025, p. 7)

Driver	Indicator (Source)	Empirical evidence (Source)
Human Resources	Involvement of researchers and experts in standardisation processes (Da Ponte et al. 2023)	Individuals' ascension to 3GPP leadership positions primarily driven by their individual achievements (Baron & Kanevskaia, 2023).
R&D	Share of 5G R&D investment over total R&D investment within top 2500 companies worldwide (EU Industrial R&D Scoreboard)	Contribution to 5G TS (Da Ponte et al. 2023)
Publications	5G related publications listed in the Web of Science (WoS).	Positive correlation with contributions to 5G standardisation (Bugghen and Blind, 2022)
Patents	Declared patents to the 5G standard, disclosed by the declaring organization (ETSI database)	Contribution to 5G TS (Da Ponte et al. 2023) Positive correlation with contributions to 5G standardisation (Bugghen and Blind, 2022)
Software	Open RAN enables interoperability among the RAN components and interfaces and. It increases the flexibility of network deployment through the development and use of open interfaces and open hardware/software (O-RAN Alliance, 2020)	Open RAN as open source initiative reacting to China's lead in 5G standardisation via patents (Kim et al. 2023)
Innovation	Share of 5G related firms over total firms (EU Industrial R&D Scoreboard)	Domestic innovation capabilities contribute to 5G TS (Da Ponte et al. 2023)
Trade	Stock of SEPs in ICT (ETSI database)	SEPs related to ICT mainly, i.e. the predecessors of 5G, promote exports and reduce import pressure (Von Laer et al. 2022)
Policy/ Regulation	The EU toolbox for 5G cybersecurity was outlined to guide Member States in tackling the main 5G-related cybersecurity risks, incl. suggestions ensuring a diverse supply chain of vetting equipment suppliers. (NIS 2020)	Securing TS by expanding number of companies being able to deliver products to public tenders and by harmonizing the regulatory frameworks incl. for public procurement across countries

5. Recommendations

To bolster the role of standardisation in achieving technological sovereignty in general and ICT in particular, several recommendations are proposed:

- support human resources for R&D, not only technologically skilled engineers but also complementary economic and strategic knowledge needed
- more courses provided by Higher Education Institutes
- interfaces of the already existing publicly funded programs to standardisation have to be extended to strengthen the role of standardisation and standards
- consider reducing participation costs for researchers related to standardisation
- improve interface between OSS and ICT standardisation
- assure that governance of standardisation bodies active in ICT to follow WTO principles plus increase inclusiveness
- look for bilateral and multilateral collaborations in international standardisation particularly in ICT
- increase diversity in supply chains via standardisation
- aligning SSOs active in ICT to needs of start-ups
- reference international standards in public procurement particularly in ICT

- using standards to promote in particular open ICT technical infrastructures

6. Challenges

Despite the potential benefits, several challenges must be addressed:

- researchers and their institutions still driven by scientific excellence and reputation (Blind et al. 2018a) or companies' interests (Blind et al. 2022a)
- whereas patents important for funding of R&D, e.g., via licensing revenues, their integration into ICT standardisation still - despite licensing regimes under FRAND conditions - challenged
- standards not used as knowledge source for product development (Grossmann et al., 2016), although they are positively correlated with product innovation (Blind et al. 2022b)
- international standards best for international trade (Swann, 2010), global value chains (Blind et al., 2018b) and preferred within trade agreements (Blind and Müller, 2018), but deviations from international standards used to protection of domestic industries
- international standards compete with policymakers' preferred national regulations (OECD, 2021), another option to implement protectionist trade policies
- international ICT standardisation consortia and OSS communities not embedded into national regulatory framework although potential to contribute to TS
- large, primarily US-based bigtechs have power to set de facto standards within global value chains (Dinges et al., 2021), which cannot be easily steered towards TS.

7. Conclusion

Standardisation is a vital tool for nations seeking to secure technological sovereignty predominantly in ICT. By establishing clear, equitable ICT standards, countries can navigate the complexities of global trade and innovation while safeguarding their national interests. Policymakers must remain proactive in fostering environments that promote effective standard-setting processes, ensuring that their nations can thrive in an increasingly competitive global landscape.

Technological sovereignty and standardisation mainly in ICT will continue to be critical topics as global dynamics evolve. Policymakers must adapt to the changing landscape, leveraging standards to enhance competitiveness and ensure that their countries can effectively respond to emerging technological challenges.

This extended synopsis provides a comprehensive overview of the key themes and insights related to ICT standardisation and technological sovereignty, emphasizing the importance of strategic policy approaches and active participation in standard-setting processes.

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